

Report on the fourth NFDI Berlin-Brandenburg network meeting:

Provenance and Reproducibility

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The series of **NFDI Berlin-Brandenburg** (NFDI_BB) meetings, kicked off in 2023, aims to build a strong network of all the NFDI consortia located in the Berlin-Brandenburg area. This successful format continues to connect individuals from various backgrounds with a common mission.

The topic of the fourth edition was „**Provenance and Reproducibility**“. In Research Data Management (RDM), these two concepts are two sides of the same coin. While provenance tells the “story” of where data came from, reproducibility is the scientific “proof” that the story can be repeated with the same results. In the workshop, all related aspects (concepts, standards, metadata, tools, . . .) of provenance and reproducibility were of interest, e.g., object biographies, RO-crates, FAIR digital objects, reproducible workflows.

The one-day workshop took place from 09:00 a.m. to 4:00 p.m. on May 19, 2026, at the headquarters of the Wikimedia Deutschland in Berlin-Kreuzberg. Around 45 participants from 18 NFDI consortia, 2 NFDI base services and allied institutions joined the meeting. For further details, see the workshop’s web site.

Figure 1: Participants of the fourth NFDI_BB meeting

Morning Session A short welcome was given by Lydia Pintscher (WMDE) and by Thomas Koprucki (WIAS) who summarized the previous meetings and gave an overview of the agenda of the day to come. To bring in some interactive element into the meeting, the welcome was followed by a Mentimeter survey operated by Aurela Shehu. The first question dealt with the attendance of previous NFDI_BB workshops. It turned out that a substantial fraction of the audience had already participated in one or more of the previous NFDI_BB workshops. Further questions concerned the workshop’s topics. Most participants were familiar with the concept of metadata, while nano-publications were known only to a few of them. With respect to the relevance of the topics, metadata and reproducibility reached the highest ranks, followed by provenance, workflows and knowledge graphs, as shown in the diagram below.

Figure 2: Mentimeter : How relevant is the topic to me?

Subsequently, in a **world café** the participants were divided into eight groups and discussed on provenance and reproducibility each on four tables. In the concluding presentations the results of the eight discussion rounds were summarized: in general, in the humanities and health sciences the provenance (source of information) was considered more important whereas in natural sciences the discussions focused more on reproducibility. However, there is a deep connection between the two concepts and together they are of key importance to the FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) .

The main obstacles to documenting **data provenance** are the additional effort required and the lack of standardization. Therefore, it is crucial to provide intuitive tools that actively assist researchers and streamline the documentation process. The participants of the world café identified a key challenge, i.e., how to overcome the lack of incentives for reporting the provenance of research data and objects. This raises a fundamental question: is provenance done for the benefit of one’s own science, or for the broader community?

Reproducibility varies by level and often degrades over time, especially as transitions to new measurement devices and computational hardware take place. A major roadblock is implicit information, i.e., the undocumented knowledge

that quietly prevents others from reproducing results. In the world café it was discussed that overcoming this would require a cultural shift within the scientific community, driven by the clear awareness that reproducibility adds long-term value to the research itself.

In a keynote representation with hands-on exercise, Daniel Mietchen introduced nano-publications which are tiny knowledge graph snippets with human and machine-interpretable metadata. Because nanopublications can be attributed and cited, they provide incentives for researchers to make their data available that drive data accessibility and interoperability. To the raised concern from the participants about the long-term existence of this service, the speaker confirmed that the service will be available in the long-term. Note that a NanoDash space was created for the fourth NFDI Berlin-Brandenburg which can be accessed at the following link.

Next, there was a round of seven talks and pitches, reflecting the diverse scientific backgrounds of the participants, ranging from humanities, e.g., culture and memory, to natural sciences and engineering, e.g. material sciences. The presenters covered both the aspects of provenance and reproducibility. For details, see the materials (partly) available here.

The afternoon started with the planning of the breakout sessions. Due to the high interest from the participants to actively contribute to the workshop and with the goal to keep the event as interactive as possible, a few contributions were scheduled for the breakout sessions. Mainly, the contributions would serve as ice breakers for the discussion to follow. Again, the materials are (partly) available online.

Summary and outlook In summary, the workshop highlighted the role of provenance and reproducibility in research data management in a variety of scientific disciplines covered in the NFDI within the Berlin-Brandenburg region. This was also investigated by means of another Mentimeter survey. The first question was which new aspects the participant learned during the workshop:

Figure 3: Mentimeter: What new did I learn today?

Clearly, nanopublications were mentioned most often, followed by object biographies. To further quantify the progress achieved during this workshop, the Mentimeter questions from the morning session were repeated. While there were no major shifts, at least it was noticed that metadata were considered even more important. Also the values for the familiarity and the relevance of nanopublications increased.

Figure 4: Mentimeter : How relevant is the topic to me?

Moreover, the workshop also served its networking aspect as shown in the diagram below. Indeed, most participants made several new contacts. This was facilitated by the open-space formats of the workshop and by the interior spaces of the building.

Figure 5: Mentimeter: How many new contacts did I make today?

Upon a final discussion with the participants, there was also the question for suggested topics for future meetings. Among the most frequent answers were research software, one NFDI, knowledge graphs, and science communication.

The next NFDI_BB meeting will take place on March 2, 2027 at the campus Griebnitzsee of the University Potsdam, organized by the colleagues from the MaRDI and the NFDIxCS consortia.

Figure 6: Mentimeter: Suggested topics for upcoming NFDI_BB workshops

Contact For feedback on this report, and for suggesting future meeting topics, please send us an email: nfdi_bb@mardi4nfdi.de

Note that the NFDI_BB mailing list will continue to be the main communication channel for information on future NFDI_BB activities:

https://www.listserv.dfn.de/sympa/info/nfdi_bb

Most of the presentations held at the meeting as well as the complete Mentimeter surveys are available at the NFDI_BB community at Zenodo,